

and 12 cm deep at 2.0 km/h or 0.56 m/s.

Of the soils tested, grey Grumusol required the highest draft, yellowish red lateritic soil the lowest (see table).

Grassy soil needed higher draft than nongrassy soil. Soil with scattered stones needed a high draft.

Wetland (previously puddled) needed a slightly lower soil draft than dryland (nonpuddled): 0.64 kN on grassy wetland, 0.57 kN on nongrassy wetland, 0.63 kN on grassy dryland, and 0.58 kN on nongrassy dryland.

The following formula calculates power required for land preparation on different soil types:

$$\text{Power (kW)} = \text{draft (kN)} \times \text{speed (m/s)}$$

For example, on vegetative grey Grumusol with a soil draft of 1.26 kN and on yellowish red lateritic with a soil draft of 0.38 kN, the required power for land preparation is 0.71 and 0.21 kW, or 0.95 and 0.28 hp, respectively. □

Table continued

Soil	Soil draft (kN)			
	Wetland		Dryland	
	Grassy	Nongrassy	Grassy	Nongrassy
Complex reddish brown Latosol and Latosol	0.58	0.49	0.50	0.49
Grey Grumusol	1.26	1.08	1.18	0.88
Old grey Grumusol	1.12	1.09	0.99	0.88
Black Grumusol	1.16	1.14	1.16	1.07
Yellowish red lateritic	0.38	0.33	0.40	0.36
Yellowish grey Regosol	0.73	0.65	0.79	0.70
Yellowish red podzolic	0.48	0.42	0.40	0.36
Yellowish brown podzolic	0.49	0.41	0.57	0.44
Brown podzolic	0.69	0.63	0.78	0.68
Violet podzolic	0.63	0.58	0.67	0.51
Brown Mediterranean	0.79	0.72	0.82	0.74
Grey Mediterranean	0.43	0.41	0.54	0.44
Complex grey brown podzolic	0.57	0.51	0.67	0.52
Complex yellowish brown Mediterranean and Latosol	0.72	0.67	0.78	0.12
Complex red Mediterranean and Latosol	0.62	0.55	0.76	0.61
Yellowish red Latosol	0.73	0.60	0.79	0.62
Reddish brown Latosol	0.60	0.50	0.64	0.60
Brown Latosol	0.88	0.77	1.02	0.79
Grey brown Regosol	0.77	0.66	0.86	0.69
Brownish yellow Latosol	0.70	0.62	0.72	0.69

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Growth and K uptake of *Azolla pinnata* under different salt levels

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We studied salt tolerance, growth, N content, acetylene reduction, and K accumulation of *Azolla pinnata* grown

under different K levels (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 ppm). The plant was grown on a N-free medium containing 40 ppm Mg, 40 ppm K, 40 ppm Ca, 20 ppm P, 0.5 ppm Mn, 0.2 ppm B, 0.1 ppm Mo, 0.01 ppm Cu, 0.01 ppm Zn, and 2 ppm Fe. Salt concentration in the control medium was 770 ppm.

To test salt tolerance, NaCl was added to the medium to make 1000, 1300, 1900, 2500, 3100, and 3700 ppm. Three grams of actively growing azolla

plants were inoculated in a plastic tray (40- × 25- × 10-cm) containing 2 liters of the test medium. Cultures were incubated at 25 ± 2 °C under fluorescent light for 16/8 h light/dark cycle. Culture medium was changed once in 3 d. Plants were harvested after 21 d.

At lower concentrations of salts (1000 and 1300 ppm), azolla grew as well as the control. Salt levels 1900 ppm and higher significantly reduced biomass production, N content, acetylene reduction activity, and K accumulation (see table). Plants were killed at 3700 ppm salt level.

Growth and K accumulation increased with increasing level of K in the culture medium. Besides fixing N of *Anabaena azollae*, azolla plants efficiently accumulated K. □

Influence of salt concentration on growth and K accumulation in *Azolla pinnata*. Baroda, India.

Total salt concentration of the medium (ppm)	Fresh weight (g)	Dry weight (g)	N content (%)	C ₂ H ₄ formed (nmol/g fresh weight per h)	K content (% by dry weight)
710	25.9	1.03	3.9	685	2.98
1000	25.7	1.02	3.9	680	2.93
1300	25.3	1.01	3.9	668	2.90
1900	17.6	0.72	3.8	530	2.61
2500	10.8	0.39	3.1	411	1.98
3100	7.2	0.07	2.8	213	1.14
LSD (0.05)	1.3	0.07	0.1	76	0.28

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